

**DETERMINATION OF COMMODITY INDICATORS (FINENESS AND
IMPURITIES) OF *NEPETA DENSIFLORA* HERB****Kuandyk A.T.****Orynbasarova K.K.**

Department of Pharmaceutical Technology and Pharmacognosy, South Kazakhstan Medical
Academy, Shymkent city, Republic of Kazakhstan

e-mail: anuar.kuandyk@gmail.com. kulpan_ok@mail.ru

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Relevance of the Research Topic: The primary source for the search of new medicinal plants is the arsenal of traditional medicine. Various species of the genus *Nepeta* (family Lamiaceae) are used in folk medicine to strengthen and stabilize the immune system, enhance the overall tone of the body, and reduce the impact of adverse environmental factors on human health.

Objective of the Study: To determine the degree of fineness and impurities through the examination of the raw material — the herb of *Nepeta densiflora*.

Materials and Methods: To determine the degree of fineness and impurities, the methodologies of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 1st edition, were applied. The object of the study was the aerial parts of *Nepeta densiflora*, growing wild in the Kaskasu area.

Results and Conclusions: An analysis of the degree of fineness and impurities of *Nepeta densiflora* herb samples was carried out. To ensure data reliability, each analysis was performed five times, after which the average result was obtained.

The determination of the degree of fragmentation was carried out using sieves (3; 2; 1; 0.5 mm).

Results of the determination of the degree of fineness: particles remaining without sieving on a 0.5 mm mesh — not more than 13%; particles remaining without sieving on a 1 mm mesh — not more than 9.6%; particles remaining without sieving on a 2 mm mesh — not more than 6.4%; particles remaining without sieving on a 3 mm mesh — not more than 5.6%.

Results of the determination of impurities: organic impurities amounted to 1.18%, while mineral impurities were 0.15%.

№	Sieve mesh diameter, mm	Amount of raw material not passed through the sieve, %	Amount of raw material passed through the sieve, %
1	3	5,6	65,2
2	2	6,4	
3	1	9,6	
4	0,5	13,2	
Total		34,8	

Conclusions: Thus, in the course of the study, the following indicators of *Nepeta densiflora* herb were obtained: organic impurities not exceeding 2% and mineral impurities not exceeding 1%, which comply with the requirements of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Kazakhstan.